

INTEGRATION OF AI TOOLS FOR ENHANCED EFFICIENCY OF LIBRARY SERVICES WITH THE DEVELOPMENT OF SMART LIBRARY

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INTRODUCTION

AI continues to grow its influence on academics, business, and other areas. Libraries are not exempt from this. While many institutions fear AI interruptions, libraries that leverage this new array of technologies will streamline everyday workflow to increase outreach efforts (FEATURE - AI Tools for Libraries, n.d.). Several AI platforms are accessible, such as ChatGPT, Microsoft's Bing Chat, Google's Bard, etc. In response to an inquiry concerning how libraries use AI to support teachers, students, and scholars on the Bard platform, the AI offered a summary of the various ways such as Tardiff, Branum, and Gustavsen use AI for research. Bard identified four categories: enhancing search results, suggesting resources, offering tailored support, and teaching and learning (Research Librarians Describe Many Ways to Use Artificial Intelligence, n.d.). Artificial intelligence (AI) technologies can be applied in various ways within libraries. According to Bently, J (2024), Artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning have gained significant attention in recent years, mainly due to the rise of chatbots like ChatGPT, Jenni, Gemini, etc. These concepts have been extensively debated in the technical and media communities. One of the initial advantages of AI language models is their capacity to respond to research queries in a syntax accessible to humans. This may emphasize the importance of users' ability to access and analyze the core content of their research flexibly. However, it is essential to note that AI integration in libraries also comes with potential risks and challenges, such as data privacy concerns, algorithmic biases, and the need for human oversight. For responsible users to verify the accuracy of AI-generated results, seamless content access.

The emergence of Artificial Intelligence (AI) has brought about a transformation in several industries, including the library. AI techniques have entirely changed how libraries function, improving their effectiveness, efficiency, and usability. This article explains how artificial intelligence (AI) might improve the effectiveness of library services and how it can help create "smart libraries."

1.1 Use of AI in Library

Libraries are considered institutions that prioritize providing services, and they have been transformed by advanced technology in the current Information Technologies (IT) age. The increasing needs of library users have necessitated librarians to adapt their service methods (Hussain, 2022a, 2022b). Even though research on AI in libraries has expanded recently, prior studies have concentrated on libraries' perceptions of AI (Wood & Evans, 2018). AI in library services will provide users with access to precise information and be a beneficial tool for the natural integration of libraries and users in the era of technological advancement. Integrating AI into library services will give users and professionals a sense of momentum. Access to humanized services at a reduced cost will be provided to readers through interaction on the same platform (Hussain, 2023).

Integrating Artificial Intelligence (AI) into library services has great potential for enhancing efficiency, accessibility, and user experience (Wheatley & Hervieux, 2019). AI can revolutionize how libraries manage their collections and assist library users in locating the resources they require. This can be achieved through automated cataloging systems, advanced recommendation techniques, etc. Artificial intelligence (AI) can potentially improve the library experience, yet its utilization and comprehension nonetheless give rise to apprehensions, particularly in developing nations. Developed countries have made significant advancements in integrating AI into their library services. However, developing countries face distinctive possibilities and obstacles in this area (Ajani et al., 2022a).

1.2 Library Challenges with Artificial Intelligence (AI)

According to certain library professionals, implementing AI in library acts presents unique challenges that must be resolved before its introduction into library services (Vijayakumar et al., K.N., 2019).

There is a concern regarding resistance to change, as specific libraries are unwilling to adopt New and revolutionary technologies. AI can suffer from the negative view of some library professionals who have inadequate knowledge of IT tools since some are not skilled in IT applications. (Hussain, 2023a).

It is imperative to address financial obstacles to integrate AI into library services.

The library may frequently lack the necessary infrastructure to support AI in its services, as AI necessitates the most advanced and sophisticated technological tools to function effectively (Ajani et al., 2022). In such cases, the library will be unable to provide AI services.

Additional challenges that must be resolved prior to the implementation of AI in library operations include the high cost of technological tools, obsolete technologies, lack of trained personnel, and poor networking services (Echedom & Okuonghae, 2022). AI will improve library operations despite these obstacles by providing timely services, cost-effectiveness, time savings, and information delivery services to existing and former users.

A significant challenge that needs to be addressed is the accessibility and accuracy of data (Arora et al., 2020). AI models depend on extensive and varied data sets to deliver precise and dependable results. However, developing nations may face challenges with data accessibility and reliability. Libraries in these countries often have restricted access to digital resources and may lack the means to digitize and preserve their collections effectively. Echedom and Okuonghae (2021) emphasized the importance of complete and demonstrative data sets to ethically and effectively apply AI in academic library services.

1.3 Using AI in Libraries to Improve User Experiences

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has become a powerful instrument, bringing about a revolution in multiple sectors. Libraries responsible for preserving knowledge and information utilize artificial intelligence (AI) to improve user experiences and make library services more accessible, thus bringing traditional library services into the digital era. The integration of AI is revolutionizing how libraries engage with their patrons and broadening the scope of accessibility in creative and unique ways.

Automated Administrative Operations: AI can streamline and mechanize regular administrative operations, like the management of book reservations, due dates, and the generation of late alerts. This automation enables library personnel to allocate more attention to aiding patrons, curating collections, and creating programs to enhance the user experience.

Innovative Recommendation Systems: Artificial intelligence-driven recommendation systems transform how libraries categorize and distribute their contents. These systems utilize data regarding user preferences, borrowing history, and reading trends to create customized reading lists and offer relevant resources. This strategy optimizes the material discovery process and enhances user engagement and satisfaction.

Chatbots and Virtual Assistants: Chatbots, powered by artificial intelligence, offer prompt support to users by responding to queries, directing them to library resources, and aiding in navigating both the digital and physical areas of the library. Virtual assistants greatly enhance accessibility by guaranteeing users can access information and assistance 24/7.

Natural Language Processing (NLP) in Research: NLP is an artificial intelligence (AI) technique that helps users in research and reference services. It assists them in creating search queries and extracting pertinent material from extensive academic databases and digital libraries. This feature expedites the research process and enhances the quality of the acquired material.

Data Analytics Powered by Artificial Intelligence: AI helps libraries build their collections by providing insightful data on how various resources are used. Analyzing this data makes making sensible choices about purchasing and maintaining resources easier, keeping the library's collection current and consistent with user preferences.

Preservation and Restoration of Materials: AI-based content analysis and optical character recognition (OCR) tools support digitalization initiatives by protecting rare and delicate materials. AI also makes restoring outdated or damaged texts easier, preserving historical records for the next generations.

Experiences with Virtual Reality (VR) and Augmented Reality (AR): AI-powered VR and AR technologies offer users immersive opportunities to explore library spaces virtually, participate in events, and engage with digital resources. These experiences enhance user engagement and expand audience reach.

Language Translation Services: Resources are accessible worldwide thanks to AI-based language translation services that libraries can use to overcome language obstacles. Customers are encouraged to be inclusive and diverse by accessing content in their chosen language.

AI integration into library services is an evolutionary change that significantly improves accessibility and user experiences. Libraries are becoming more dynamic, inclusive, and user-centric using AI technologies. This is because they are making knowledge and information accessible to everyone, which promotes an informed and enriched population (Ashikuzzaman & Ashikuzzaman, 2023).

SMART LIBRARY FRAMEWORK IN ACADEMIC LIBRARY

Over the past decade, the new technology revolution has enabled brilliant libraries to incorporate intelligence into various aspects. This includes the physical space, organization of information resources (knowledge), service modes, and management methods. These advancements have been made possible by utilizing technologies such as the Internet of Things, big data, cloud computing, RFID technology, artificial intelligence, and virtual reality. The primary goal of Smart Library is to enhance the efficiency and quality of services for users, establish an appealing environment for information interconnectivity, and foster a diverse space for exchanging knowledge. The advanced use cases of an intelligent library encompass a 24-hour self-service system for borrowing and returning books, a mobile phone/network system for self-renewal of borrowed materials, an intelligent system for inventory management and item positioning, an innovative system for reserving seats, and a cutting-edge 3D/AR/VR navigation system, among others (Yu et al., 2019).

Fig 1: Smart Library Framework

2.1 AI Integration in Smart Library

Since the development of the computer Deep Blue in 1997 and the computer program AlphaGo in 2016, there has been a continuous display of board game competitions between machines and

humans, consistently showcasing advancements in Artificial Intelligence (AI) technology to the open to everyone. Humans have ambivalent feelings towards the achievements of AI-based robots in games against humans. Human beings are enthusiastic about the transformative impact that AI will have on our lives. On the other hand, the potential for AI to replace most human labor could result in restricted employment opportunities and hinder human economic progress (Nie et al., 2022; Adams, 2024).

AI-Based Subject Indexing: AI and automation solutions can effectively address the issues related to subject indexing arising from the growing number of resources and documents. Artificial intelligence tools in libraries possess advanced functionalities that enable them to Extract subjects, keywords, and other data from book text and image files. These technologies enable more accurate indexing by automatically classifying materials, assigning subject headings, and understanding the relationships between concepts. Artificial intelligence can effectively evaluate user reviews, comments, and search trends to improve the accuracy of topic access and metadata processes. Annie is a tool created by the National Library of Finland to simplify the process of human-made automated subject indexing.

AI-Based Cataloguing: Artificial Intelligence (AI) in library automation technology can expedite the process of cataloging books, journals, and other items in the library. Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) algorithms can assess enormous amounts of data to automatically classify and organize library materials, create bibliographic records from digital files, suggest suitable subject headings, and combine catalog data with external knowledge bases depending on pertinent content. For example, it has been stated that the Library of Congress is using artificial intelligence to optimize the cataloging process by producing automatically generated bibliographic data and standardizing catalog records. AI and automation technologies may drastically cut down on labor and guarantee uniformity throughout the cataloging process, free from mistakes and inconsistencies.

Fig 2: AI-based Cataloging Service

Reservation Management: Artificial intelligence-driven library software gathers pertinent data about the resources checked out from devices like QR and RFID readers to streamline and automate the check-out procedure. With the help of this feature, users may make online reservations for resources, look up available resources, get immediate updates on the availability of resources, get alerts for overdue things, and get automated notifications when the item is ready for loan.

Inventory and Stock Management: The processes involved in managing library stocks and inventories used to be challenging and complicated. On the other hand, demand forecasting, intelligent shelving, reorder point calculation, safety stock calculation, intelligent inventory optimization, and multi-location inventory management are all efficiently carried out by libraries' AI inventory and stock management systems. Artificial intelligence (AI) technologies can locate library inventory and stock levels, find frequently used items, and optimize shelf space by utilizing insights from RFID tags and devices. In addition, these sophisticated automation technologies can forecast resource usage, book requirements, stock shortages, and more.

Document Processing: Library staff manually process and update various library documents, a common and costly task that can now be readily accomplished with AI and automation. When combined with machine learning algorithms and technologies like scanning, optical character recognition, and

image processing, artificial intelligence tools can easily automate library information retrieval, data validation, and document analysis processes.

Fig 3: AI-Based Inventory and Stock Management

Electronic Resource Management: Library automation systems facilitate digitizing resources such as books, journals, and databases. However, AI can help ensure these electronic resources are managed without errors. Effective electronic resource management allows users to quickly and easily access various digital materials from a vast collection, including e-books and e-journals. This facilitates monitoring resource access, fine collection, due dates, reservations, and other relevant library information.

Automated Circulation: Self-service portals, radio frequency identification (RFID), and other powerful features are included in AI-based library services to automate the check-in and check-out of books. The data is transferred to RFID reader-enabled self-service portals via the RFID tags inserted into the books, which expedites the loaning, returning, and renewing of books. This will ensure that waiting times for other services are reduced and the long lines at the libraries can be minimized.

Virtual Learning: Improving user learning and virtual instruction are two further beneficial uses of AI-based library systems. Adaptive learning platforms, automated content curation, feedback surveys, assessment forms, book augmented reality, personalized learning paths, and immersive experiences can all be achieved in libraries using artificial intelligence systems. Additionally, they can be combined with virtual assistants to improve learning outcomes, enhance student engagement, and help students learn more efficiently.

Fig 4: AI-Based Virtual Learning

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Digital technologies such as automation and artificial intelligence are rapidly changing academic, public, and private libraries today. These technologies make library operations like document processing, subject indexing, cataloging, and customer service more efficient. Because automation and artificial

intelligence are developing technologically, library automation tools will become more functional. Several contemporary libraries, like Stanford University Libraries, Palo Alto City Library, Penn Library, and San Jose Public Library, are already investing in automation and artificial intelligence (AI) to improve their services and operations. In the coming years, library users may be able to visit completely automated, human-free AI libraries, given the speed at which AI is being introduced into libraries. The education system will transform due to the influence of artificial intelligence. The library's significance as a hub for social education, learning, knowledge, and communication will increase, allowing for more significant opportunities for its growth and expansion. Implementing artificial intelligence technology in libraries aims to augment and promote information sharing and interpersonal relationships rather than replacing librarians. Consequently, libraries should reconsider their stance on the implementation of artificial intelligence. Individuals should have a more favorable stance towards artificial intelligence and actively contribute to enhancing library services' communication capabilities and efficiency. The intelligent library concept is characterized by a certain degree of ambiguity, as it is flexible, open, and constantly evolving. Modifying the widely recognized definition provided by Giffinger. An innovative library can be described as highly efficient and forward-thinking, functioning as a central hub for knowledge. It offers access to a wide range of information and enhances individuals' ability to understand and utilize information effectively. The concept pertains to the exploration and recognition of intelligent solutions that enable contemporary libraries to improve the caliber of their services. Technologically influenced library activities are transforming the reading and learning environment, even as electronic media becomes more prevalent. However, traditional books will never become obsolete. Academic libraries worldwide have been significantly influenced by the recent advancements in information technology and the evolving learning environment. Libraries should comprehend the changes occurring in the academic, research, and general community and adapt accordingly to stay in sync with worldwide trends. A library can enhance its service quality, introduce new services, and adopt new information technology, regardless of whether it is considered intelligent.

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